

Role of low molecular weight additives on the early-stages of magnesium carbonate mineralization

Encarnacion Ruiz-Agudo^{1*}, *Lisa Huber*², *Sarah Bonilla-Correa*¹, *Francesco Santoro De Vico*¹, *Cristina Ruiz-Agudo*², and *Carlos Rodriguez-Navarro*¹

¹Department of Mineralogy and Petrology, University of Granada, Avenida Fuentenueva s/n, 18002 Granada Spain

²Department of Chemistry, University of Konstanz, Universitätsstraße 10, 78457 Konstanz Germany

Abstract. The early stages of MgCO₃ formation remain highly unexplored as compared to CaCO₃. Recent studies have shown that MgCO₃ precipitation is non-classic and involves the formation of amorphous magnesium carbonate (AMC) prior to the stable carbonate phase. Here, the synthesis of AMC was carried out at constant alkaline pH using a potentiometric titration setup. We investigated the influence of sodium citrate and acetate, low molecular weight additives, on the nucleation, growth, and stability of AMC and its recrystallization, enabling tailored control over its formation for both environmental and engineering applications. These additives delay AMC nucleation and significantly impact its stability, and their presence in solution result in its recrystallization into less hydrated crystalline MgCO₃ phases

Introduction

Processes taking place during MgCO₃ formation have important implications in natural and technological processes. On the Earth's surface, carbonation occurs through the chemical weathering of Ca²⁺, Mg²⁺ and/or Fe²⁺ primary silicates, which releases cations to the ecosystems that react with CO₂ dissolved in natural waters. This mechanism reduces atmospheric CO₂ and regulates the Earth's climate over geologic timescales. Thus, significant research has focused on mimicking this process for long-term CO₂ storage. Additionally, the mineral phase, morphology, and microstructural evolution of magnesium carbonates formed upon carbonation of dolomitic lime, are all key parameters influencing the physico-mechanical properties and performance of mortars and plasters. In these and other scenarios, early-stage processes occurring during MgCO₃ formation may significantly impact the stability, morphology, and size of the final crystalline phase (e.g. [1]), and thus it is crucial to obtain a deep understanding of these processes to be ultimately able to control carbonation reactions. Comparatively, the early stages of MgCO₃ formation remain highly unexplored as compared to CaCO₃, and only a few studies have been performed aimed at elucidating how these early stages are impacted by the presence of additives. Here, the synthesis of magnesium carbonate was carried out at constant alkaline pH using a potentiometric titration setup. We aim at investigating the influence of sodium citrate and acetate, low molecular weight additives, on the nucleation, growth, and stability of MgCO₃ phases, enabling tailored control over its formation for both environmental and engineering applications.

* Corresponding author: encaruiz@ugr.es

Methodology

MgCO₃ precipitation experiments were carried out at a fixed pH of 11, maintained by NaOH addition using a Titrino 905 (Methrom). A 100 mM MgCl₂ solution was continuously added at a rate of 0.12 mL min⁻¹ to a 50 mM K₂CO₃ buffer. Tri-sodium citrate dihydrate (0.04 to 5 mM) was added to the carbonate buffer. pH, solution conductivity, and transmittance were monitored during the duration of the experiments. Once the precipitation experiment was completed, the reaction media was filtered using Nucleopore membranes ($\phi = 200$ nm) to separate the solids, which were subsequently analyzed by X-ray diffraction using a PANalytical X'Pert Pro X-ray diffractometer (Cu K α radiation, $\lambda = 1.5405$ Å, 3 to 50° 2 θ range, 0.11° 2 θ s⁻¹ scanning rate). Further characterization was performed using Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) with a ATRproONE-FTIR spectrometer (Jasco, model 6600) (frequency range 400-4000 cm⁻¹, resolution 2 cm⁻¹; 100 accumulations), and thermogravimetry and differential scanning calorimetry (TGA/DSC) with a Mettler-Toledo TGA/DSC equipment (25-950°C, 10 K/min heating rate, 120 mL/min flowing air).

Results and discussion

XRD results confirmed the amorphous character of the precipitates, with and without additives. Also, the titration experiments revealed the strong nucleation inhibition exerted by citrate. Before precipitation, a continuous decrease in the conductivity of the solution was measured, which can be related to the formation of ion associates (i.e. any solution species containing Mg²⁺ and CO₃²⁻). Analytical ultracentrifugation (AUC) measurements demonstrated the presence of ion associates during the early stages of MgCO₃ formation (i.e. prenucleation clusters, PNCs) [2]. PNCs formation and aggregation are key processes for AMC nucleation; both are hampered by acetate and, particularly, citrate. This inhibits the nucleation of AMC and allows the system to cross the spinodal limit and the formation of a dense liquid precursor prior to AMC. After aging for one week, AMC recrystallized into nesquehonite (MgCO₃·3H₂O) -in the case of control runs and acetate-bearing experiments- and dypingite (Mg₅(CO₃)₄(OH)₂·5H₂O) -in the presence of citrate-. The additives also delay the recrystallization of AMC into the final crystalline phase.

Conclusions

Citrate and acetate delay MgCO₃ (AMC) nucleation and significantly impact its stability, and their presence in solution result in its recrystallization into less hydrated crystalline MgCO₃ phases, enabling tailored control over its formation for both environmental and engineering applications.

This research has been funded by the EC (ACT_ERA NET no. 691712, PCI2019-111931-2 and H2020 ETN-ITN SUBLime -grant agreement n° 955986-), the Spanish Government (grant PID2021-125305NB-I00) and University of Granada (Unidad Científica de Excelencia UCE-PP2016-05).

References

1. J. Elsen, M.D. Jackson, E. Ruiz-Agudo, Historic Concrete Science: Opus Caementicium to “Natural Cements”. Elements 18, 301-307 (2022). A. Nicolas, J.-L. Barrat, J. Rottler, Effects of inertia on the steady-shear rheology of disordered solids. Phys. Rev. Lett. 116, 058303 (2016)
2. A. Verch, M. Antonietti, H. Colfen, Mixed calcium-magnesium prenucleation clusters enrich calcium. (2012) Zeitschrift Fur Kristallographie-Crystalline Materials 227, 718-722 (2012)